

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS USING GAME TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: In this article, there is a scientific discussion about the importance of using game technologies in increasing the educational activities of primary school students and the main tasks of improving the methodology.

Key words: pedagogical activity, educational system, game technologies, analysis, primary education, diagnostics, reproductive activity.

Introduction:

School lessons are the way to the heights of knowledge, the intellectual growth of the student and the process of its improvement. In each of them, ideas and incredible discoveries are born by elementary school students that awaken children's minds. But despite all their charm, lessons can have a negative character, that is, they are not interesting for students, they involve boredom and idleness. Therefore, the value of the lesson lies in the teacher and how he presents it. Emphasizing the importance of providing educational material, as Anatole Franz said: "knowledge absorbed with appetite is better absorbed", for this the teacher must be able to properly use well-known pedagogical techniques and methodologies, among which I can note game technologies. On the example of these technologies, I reveal the value of games in the lesson, which can be interesting with their help, where children themselves are attracted to the material.

When choosing games and game exercises, it is necessary to take into account the educational interests of students, as well as the preserved intellectual qualities of each student's personality, which help the child to demonstrate his abilities, provide a level of independence in the search for knowledge. are games. It is also necessary to develop a system of incentives for success, but not for the victory of the student or group of students, but for demonstrating the application of new skills in the game. An important premise is that you need to take into account the level of knowledge of elementary school students, because providing an option for more complex games, due to the failures of the task, the interest of junior school students may be lost. It is not difficult to get elementary school students interested in writing, reading or mathematics, because the most common solution for learning spelling rules by exercises, examples or children is that the work can be very interesting, the main thing is to present an interesting character. For example, identify the children's favorite fairy-tale characters, and let this favorite character ask for help from the guys - then even a student who is behind in the school curriculum will come to the help of his hero and demonstrate some educational activity. The use of competitive elements is great, because the form of the game involves students in the process and allows them to demonstrate leadership qualities.

Instead of the teacher's usual introduction at the beginning of the lesson, you can use a game technique such as a riddle. Pupils are offered rebus, drawings, task cards and their goal is to reveal the name of the subject of the lesson. Also, an interesting game exercise for elementary school students "make the right decision and read". Posters with numbers and letters are hung on the board, the student must solve the column of examples and write the corresponding letter next to the example. The result should be some words spoken by the teacher. This work can be done by one student in the class or a group of students. This exercise is used in math class and also helps students to remember the spelling of a certain letter faster.

"Anagram" game in the Russian language class can be well suited for developing students' intellectual mental activity. A set of scattered letters is given and students have to make a word from the given number of letters. A game like "Conclusions" is also used. Choose two words from the brackets that are most important to the word before the brackets. "Conclusions" example:

- 1. Garden (plant, gardener, dog, fence, land).**
- 2. River (shore, fish, Tina, Fisherman, water).**
- 3. Reading (eyes, book, picture, print, glasses).**
- 4. Game (chess, players, rules, penalties, punishments).**

The game "language ratio" is suitable for the topic studied in the 3rd grade "Antonyms and synonyms". Here the teacher can improvise with food and material, color cards can be distributed, you can depict on the board using prepared posters, cut leaves and tie it to a flower, and the students' task is to choose an antonym or a synonym for the presented word.

These games help to form cognitive competences in Russian language and literature classes, in the surrounding world. The following games are suitable for combining material, repeating, explaining a new topic.

These games are used in the mathematics lesson: "who is faster" is offered to collect objects from geometric shapes, "find the error" numbers are given, the order is broken or the number is written incorrectly, students must find the error and correct it. "Intellectual warm-up" this game helps to expand the worldview of a young student. Children are asked a series of questions, understanding how to quickly answer them, you can conduct this game in a blitz survey. An example of changing the questions themselves:

- 1. How many fingers are there on both hands?**
- 2. How many weeks in a month?**
- 3. Friday serial number of the week?**
- 4. What is the last day of the year?**

These questions can be accompanied by pictures that serve as clues for the students. And if it is difficult to answer, the teacher can ask leading questions, thereby giving advice for answering this exercise. In case of failure, if the class does not find the correct answer, the teacher can always suggest the students to think about the exercise and return to it after some time with new ideas and strength.

I can note that it is good to do vocabulary dictation with the help of puzzles, crosswords, because students are not afraid of the testing environment and easily complete the task in one breath, making a small number of mistakes in words. In turn, riddles help to develop imaginative thinking, the ability to distinguish important features, teach the speed and flexibility of the mind. Different variations of games in "Words" enrich the child's vocabulary,

as well as renew the passive vocabulary. The main aspect of the implementation of game technologies in the lesson is not to turn the lesson into a game, but to observe the time to get more material and give the children additional excitement. To develop the imagination and creativity of primary school students, games such as "picture story", "fill in the sentence" are used.

The peculiarity of game technologies is that they allow to make one or another generalization, to understand the rules that have just been learned, to deeply master the material and acquired knowledge in the system, in new connections, and in depth of the past ones. Didactic games are easily used at absolutely any stage of the lesson: at the beginning, they help to understand the educational material, and in the middle - to activate the learning activity of elementary school students or to consolidate and systematize new concepts.

The material learned during the game activity is forgotten by students to a lesser extent than the material that was not used in the game. This is explained, first of all, by the fact that the game organically combines entertainment, makes the learning process convenient and interesting for elementary school students.

Thus, game technologies allow you to teach the material in a convenient, interesting way, contribute to better acquisition of knowledge, arouse interest in knowledge in elementary school students, and build students' cognitive abilities. The use of game techniques depends on the professional skills and creativity of the teacher, who can diversify the techniques and forms of work.

In fact, it can be said that play is a very powerful tool for influencing a child's personality. The game is a powerful learning stimulus, diverse and powerful learning motivation. The game plays an important educational role in human life, and it also has a great impact on the development of creative imagination, which is very necessary in the further work of a young student.

We found that games form the most positive qualities for interpersonal relationships. Because in the game, the child learns moral standards and rules of behavior, and also learns to communicate with both adults and peers.

My research has shown that play is an effective learning tool. It makes the learning process much easier, attracts students with different work speeds and materials. During the game, a positive emotional state is guaranteed, the young student's ability to work increases, the game helps to relieve children's fatigue, and also increases the motivation to learn.

A feature of a pedagogical game that differs from ordinary everyday games is a clearly defined educational goal and pedagogical results corresponding to it, which is characterized by a cognitive orientation.

Conclusion:

Thus, it can be said with confidence that if you include game technologies in the educational process, as well as combine them with other pedagogical technologies, the educational process of primary school students will be more effective. My research has shown that the distinctive feature of game technologies is their positive impact on the process of teaching and educating schoolchildren, which leads to great achievements in the field of student knowledge. This game technique is recorded during the course work.

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